

LIQUID-PHASE PROCESSES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF IRON AND STEEL FROM RAW MATERIALS

Mashkhura Idilloevna Sadikova
Khudoyberdiev Muhammed
Uralov Dilshod

Bukhara State Technical University
Students of group 202-24.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17990835>

Annotatsiya: This article examines the liquid-phase process for iron and steel production. International experience in the steel industry is presented. A continuous process for smelting steel and iron in ore-thermal furnaces has been developed, allowing the use of 100% metallized raw materials in the charge. The process was tested in an experimental industrial ore-thermal furnace with a capacity of 1200 kVA on pellets obtained from the metallized Lebedinsky and Kachkanarsky deposits under the conditions of the Beloretsk Metallurgical Plant. In total, about 600 tons of metallized pellets were obtained with a waste rock content of up to 15% and a metallization degree of 85-95%.

Key words: metallized granules, direct production of steel and iron.

The global metallurgical industry has reached a stage of development at which further technical and technological re-equipment within the framework of the development of new steelmaking processes is becoming increasingly important. This is driven by the need to reduce energy, labor and capital costs, optimize production flexibility and control environmental pollution.

Recently, new direct production processes have been developed that are becoming competitive with blast furnaces. This is due to capital expenditure on coke ovens, ore enrichment (pellet production and sintering, gas cleaning equipment and the blast furnace itself), which, according to Western experts, exceed one billion dollars [1].

In this regard, liquid-phase reduction processes are being developed. These are divided into single-stage, block-based processes, and two-stage processes, in which the starting materials are heated and reduced in separate chambers of one block, and then reheated and melted in another. Below are a number of liquid phase recovery processes that have been tested around the world. The process is carried out in a gasifier of a smelting plant operating in conjunction with a shaft furnace for the production of sponge iron. The raw materials used are iron ore, iron ore pellets, and non-coking coal as an agglomerate and reducing agent. Industrial tests at the KR pilot plant with a capacity of 60 thousand tons of cast iron per year showed the possibility of obtaining... cast iron with the following composition: C-4-4.4%; Si 1.3%; S-0.02 - 0.04% and a metal melting point of 1500-1550 °C [2].

The process involves mixing iron ore pellets with coal dust, crushing and granulating them, then drying and heating the resulting pellets to 1000°C in a hydraulically sealed Dwight-Lloyd conveyor. The resulting metallized product is continuously fed into a submersible electric furnace. The furnace capacity is 200-400 tons per day. To produce 1 ton of pig iron using the McDowell-Wellman process, the following is consumed: 1.4-1.9 tons of iron ore; 0.6-0.9 tons of coal; 0.2-0.6 tons of flux; 750-1000 kWh of electricity; 1.8-4.5 kg of electrodes. Thus, the described methods of direct production have a continuous technological process and less

pollution compared to the blast furnace converter process, low specific capital investments, especially for small production units.

The Elred process (Sweden) was developed by Stora Konnarberg and ACEA [3-6]. The process involves pre-reduction of iron ore fines in a fluidized bed reactor and final reduction in a direct current arc furnace. The initial reduction is carried out with pulverized coal blown into the reactor with air at 950 °C. The final reduction is carried out in a direct current arc furnace at 1450 °C. The pre-reduced product with a metallization degree of 60-70% is discharged from the bottom of the reactor, cooled to 700 °C and continuously charged into the arc furnace through a hollow carbon electrode, together with slag-forming additives. To better separate the slag from the metal, foamed slag is used. Cast iron contains about 3.5% C; 0.5% Si; 0.5% Mn. The semi-finished product has a high content of Si and P introduced by the raw materials, therefore, subsequent dephosphorization and desulfurization are required. The company "Boliden" developed the "Inred" process (Sweden), which is based on heating iron ore fines and coal dust to high temperatures, pre-reduction to vusite in a suspended melting chamber, and final reduction in an arc furnace [7-9]. The suspended melting chamber is located above the arc furnace. In the first stage, the ore fines are re-melted and reduced to FeO. Remelting occurs in a melting cyclone at a temperature of 1900 °C. The energy source is coal burned in a stream of oxygen. The second stage of the process takes place in an electric furnace. The remaining coal, which has been converted into coke, reacts with FeO to form sponge iron, which is carbonized and melted. The resulting liquid pig iron is tapped for a period of time, having the following chemical composition: C 3-4%; Si 0.5-1%; and a large amount of phosphorus. Since the phosphorus contained in the iron ore is transferred to the pig iron, it undergoes dephosphorization and desulfurization.

A distinctive feature of the process is the formation of a stable plasma cone into which the charging materials can be directly injected. The plasmatron unit is mounted on the refractory lining of the furnace roof with the plasmatron axis tilted from the vertical by 5-15 °C; the water-cooled part of the plasmatron extends into the working area of the furnace. The plasmatron control and its rotation frequency are determined by the requirements of the technology. As the plasmatron rotates, it forms an arc cone. It is found that at a certain rotation frequency, the cone has high stability, which allows the powder-charged material to be injected directly into the cone. The injected material particles are captured by the plasma cone, directly exposed to the electrical forces of the plasma, and rapidly heated. This process can produce low-carbon, low-sulfur steel in one step.

Thus, the described methods of direct production have a continuous technological process and less pollution compared to the blast furnace converter process, low specific capital investments, especially for small production units.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Ramazanov B., Juraeva L., Sharipova N. Synthesis of modified amino-aldehyde oligo (poly) mers and study of their thermal stability //IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. – IOP Publishing, 2021. – T. 839. – №. 4. – C. 042096.
2. Akhmedov V., Jumaev J., Sharipova N. Influence of the nature and quantity of the catalyst on the synthesis of morpholine unsaturated products with the participation of vinyl acetylene //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 58-61.

3. Phozilov S. P. et al. Development of Technology for Depressor Additives for Diesel Production from Polymer Wastes //Young Scientist USA. – 2014. – Т. 35. – С. 45.
4. Шарипова Н. У. Химическая промышленность и окружающая среда //Universum: химия и биология. – 2022. – №. 5-1 (95). – С. 19-21.
5. Мухамадиев Б. Т., Шарипова Н. У. Нетепловые механизмы действия электромагнитного поля (ЭМП) низких частот (нч) на растительное сырье //Universum: химия и биология. – 2020. – №. 6 (72). – С. 89-91.
6. Шарипова Н. У., Мухамадиев Б. Т., Шарипова Н. У. ХРАНЕНИЕ, ТРАНСПОРТИРОВКА И РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ КРИО ИЗМЕЛЬЧЕННЫХ И ЗАМОРОЖЕННЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ РАСТИТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 2-2 (83). – С. 100-103.
7. Жумаев Ж. Х., Шарипова Н. У. Структурно-механические характеристики композиций на основе электрохимического модифицированного крахмала и полимеров //Universum: химия и биология. – 2019. – №. 11-1 (65). – С. 74-76.
8. Sharipova, N., & Ismatilloeva, G. (2025). OBTAINING ADHESIVES FROM LOCAL RAW MATERIALS. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 4, Выпуск 65, сс. 92–95).
9. Шарипова, Н., Улмасова, Д., Эрдонова, Ш., & Ахмедова, У. (2025). ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ АДГЕЗИВНЫХ ВЕЩЕСТВ ИЗ МЕСТНОГО СЫРЬЯ. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 4, Выпуск 65, сс. 96–99).